

Highlights

Prison data from C-EHRN
monitoring report 2025

38 European cities with prisons reported:

Only 1 out of 38 cities reported having all 4 key harm reduction services available in prison.

3x less Naloxone Distribution

7x less Needle and Syringe Programmes

In prison compared to the general community

Drug use does not stop at the prison gate, neither should Harm reduction.

Correlation

European Harm
Reduction Network

Harm Reduction in European Prisons

Availability and Current Gaps

Civil Society Monitoring of Harm Reduction
in Europe **2025**

Correlation

 European Harm
Reduction Network

Title

Harm Reduction in European prisons: Availability and Current Gaps. Civil Society Monitoring of Harm Reduction In Europe 2025.

Authors

De Sousa, M.: Conceptualisation; Investigation; Data curation; Writing- Original Draft; Formal analysis; Visualisation; **Rigoni, R.:** Conceptualisation; Methodology; Writing- Review & Editing; Supervision; Project Administration; **C-EHRN Focal Points:** Data provision; Validation.

Contributing C-EHRN Focal Points

Antwerp - Free Clinic - Tessa Windelick; **Athens** - Positive Voice - Konstantina Papastefanaki; **Balti** - The Union for Equity and Health - Ala Iatco; **Barcelona** - Red Cross Catalonia, Department of Health of the Red Cross, Drug Addiction Area - Penelope Aguilera; **Belgrade** - Regeneration - Irena Molnar; **Berlin** - Fixpunkt e. V. - Astrid Leicht; **Berlin** - Deutsche Aidshilfe - Dirk Schaeffer; **Bern** - Infodrog / Radix - Marc Marthaler; **Bielefeld** - Drogenberatung e.V. Bielefeld - Jan-Gert Hein; **Bratislava** - Odysseus - Miriama Michal Hrehová; **Bucharest** - Romanian Association Against AIDS (ARAS) - Alina Bocai; **Budapest** - Rights Reporter Foundation - Peter Sarosi; **Copenhagen** - HealthTeam for the Homeless Copenhagen - Henrik Thiesen; **Dublin** - Ana Liffey Drug Project - Damien Gagnevin; **Gdańsk** - Prekursor Foundation for Social Policy - Magdalena Bartnik; **Glasgow** - Scottish Drugs Forum - Kirsten Horsburgh; **Helsinki** - Ehyt Ry - Kim Kannussaari; **Helsinki** - A-Clinic Foundation - Juha Sedergren; **Krakow** - MONAR-Krakow - Judyta Put; **Kyev** - NGO Club Eney - Velta Parkhomenko; **Lisbon** - Ares do Pinhal - Hugo Faria; **Ljubljana** - Stigma - Ana Vujičić; **London** - Release - Shayla Schlossenberg; **Milano** - Fondazione LILA Milano - Maria Luisa Cosmaro, Sandra Curridori- Cooperativa Lotta contro l'Emarginazione- Cristiano Bregamo, Paolo Di Gloria; **Munich** - Condrops - Olaf Ostermann; **Nicosia** - Cyprus National Addictions Authority - Evi Kyprianou; **Paris** - Fédération Addiction - Marine Gaubert; **Podgorica** - Juventas - Marija Mijovic; **Porto e VnGaia** - APDES - Jose Queiroz; **Prague** - SANANIM z.ú. - David Pesek; **Reykjavík** - Matthildur - Svala Jóhannesdóttir; **Riga** - DIA+LOGS - Ruta Kaupe; **Rome** - Forum Droghe - Antonella Camposegrana; **Skopje** - Healthy Option Project Skopje - HOPS - Blagorodna Koceva Simjanov; **Sofia** - Center for Humane Policy - Yuliya Georgieva; **Tallinn** - OÜ ReCuro - Greete Org; **Tbilisi** - Georgian Harm Reduction Network - Maka Gogia; **Tirana** - Aksion Plus - Genci Mucollari; **Vienna** - Suchthilfe Wien gGmbH - Marcus Ramusch; **Vilnius** - Coalition "I Can Live" - Laura Bliujiene; **Warsaw** - Prekursor Foundation for Social Policy - Magdalena Bartnik; **Zurich** - Drug Information Center (DIZ) -Dominique Schori

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c/o De Regenboog Group | Stadhouderskade 159 | 1074BC Amsterdam | The Netherlands

www.correlation-net.org

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Drug use does not stop at the prison gate, neither should Harm Reduction.

→ Approximately **1.4 Million people** are currently in prison in Europe, 500k in the EU alone [1][2].

→ **Drug use in prisons is higher than in the general population**, up to 60x times higher for some substances [3]. Many individuals start using drugs in prison: around 1 in 3 people who use drugs inside prison started after imprisonment [4].

→ **Infectious diseases** are high in prison settings, with Hepatitis C (HCV) prevalence reaching up to 84% in prison populations in some countries [5][6].

→ Drug overdose is a common cause of death in prison: **1 in 10 violent deaths in prison** are due to intentional or accidental drug **overdose** or intoxication [4].

→ In recent years, a substantial rise in **New Psychoactive Substances** has created added challenges that impact the entire prison environment and the (mental) health of people in prison [7][8].

Drug-related risks in prisons are high. Harm reduction services are essential to protect incarcerated individuals.

Figure 1: Map of European cities that participated in C-EHRN prison monitoring questionnaire 2025

Availability of harm reduction services in prison remains limited

Naloxone, NSP not available in most cities

Across the 38 cities included in the 2025 C-EHRN Monitoring that reported having a prison, the **availability of essential harm reduction services was uneven**. OAT (36) and HCV (33) testing were reported far more often than naloxone distribution (6) and needle and syringe programmes (5).

OAT and HCV testing alone is not sufficient. Naloxone can prevent fatal overdose, including in the period around release, when overdose risk rises markedly.

The EU Drugs Action Plan 2021–2025 calls for overdose awareness training and, where possible, take-home naloxone upon release [10]. It also supports evidence-based prison measures to prevent drug-related deaths and reduce transmission of blood-borne infections. NSPs in prisons are therefore not an optional add-on as they help reduce unsafe injecting and lower the risk of hepatitis C and other blood-borne conditions.

Complementary HR services remain absent

Alongside these key harm reduction services, there are additional responses fundamental in prison settings. In recent years, there was a reported shift in prison drug markets, marked by the increasing availability of New Psychoactive Substances (NSP). These substances brought additional challenges, due to high unpredictability [9]. NPS are also associated with severe psychiatric and physical effects such as agitation, psychosis, seizures, cardiovascular problems and in some cases overdoses [8][9].

Availability of Key Harm Reduction Services in Prisons

Opioid Agonist Treatment (36/38)

Hepatitis C (HCV) Testing (33/38)

Naloxone Distribution (6/38)

Needle and Syringe Programs (5/38)

Figure 2: Availability of four key harm reduction services in prison across 38 European cities.

Availability of complementary HR services in prisons

Figure 3: Availability of complementary harm reduction services in prison across 38 European cities

Fewer than 10 cities reported availability of written **information on drug use and risk behaviour** as well as written information on **harm reduction services** and materials. Only 7 cities reported **overdose awareness and responses training**. This is concerning as prison staff needs the knowledge, training, and practical tools to respond.

Gap: European prisons still show limited preparedness to recognise or respond to challenges brought by NSPs as they lack complementary harm reduction services.

— Only 1/38 cities reported having all 4 key prison HR services

Comprehensive prison harm reduction was reported in just **1 out of 38 cities**. In other words, only one city reported all four key harm reduction services. That is not a small gap in coverage, it shows that a **full prison harm reduction response remains exceptional rather than standard**.

Variety of key HR services in prison, per city (n=38 cities)

- Cities with no key services
- Cities with 1 key service type
- Cities with 2 key services types
- Cities with 3 key services types
- Cities with all key services types

Figure 4: Variety in reported number of key harm reduction services available in each city

— Need to expand prison HR beyond partial coverage

Our findings highlight that harm reduction services in prisons remain **fragmented** and **outdated**. OAT, HCV testing, Naloxone distribution and NSPs should not be seen as separate measures, but **should function as an integrated harm reduction package**, working together to reduce opioid overdose risk and prevent the transmission of infectious diseases in prison settings.

The current situation falls short of existing international and European policy and public health standards.

The Madrid Recommendation (2009) calls for harm reduction in prison, including opioid substitution therapy, needle and syringe programmes, infectious disease screening and treatment, mental health support, staff training, and throughcare on entry and after release [11]. Likewise, the EU Drugs Action Plan 2021–2025 calls for equivalence and continuity of healthcare in prison, including overdose prevention, and take-home naloxone on release [10].

This is not a new policy gap. Some of these recommendations have been published for over 15 years, yet prison harm reduction remains incomplete.

Countries must establish a national minimum standard for prison harm reduction, applicable in all prison settings.

→ Following Council of Europe guidance, national policymakers and prison health authorities should define a standard with the basic level of harm reduction that all prisons are expected to provide [13].

→ Prison authorities and local governments should then work together to implement these standards in practice, so that availability does not depend on individual prison leadership, or institutional preference.

Learning from practice: Naloxone distribution in Iceland

In Iceland, a new prison naloxone initiative was developed in response to growing overdose concern. Matthildur (C-EHRN focal point in Iceland), Afstada, and the Prison and Probation Administration worked together to introduce naloxone training in every prison unit, adapting training sessions to each individual setting and delivering them with peer involvement [12]. The sessions covered opioid risks, signs of overdose, and how to use naloxone. After the training, naloxone nasal spray was made available in those units. This has resulted in naloxone being available across all prison units in Iceland, with anonymous access for people in prison [12]. Read full interview with Matthildur [here](#).

Harm reduction services in prison vs in the general community

EUDA data shows that drug use is more common among the prison population compared to the general population, even up to 40x higher for some substances [14].

This raises an important question: **if harm reduction services exist in a city, do they also reach people in prison?**

HR in prisons up to 7x less available

For OAT and HCV testing, availability in prison was close to availability in the community, meaning that in most cities where these services were reported outside prison, they were also reported inside prison. In contrast, a pronounced disparity emerged for naloxone and NSP. **Naloxone** was available **4x** more often in the community than in prison, while **NSPs** were available **7.4x** more often outside prison.

This shows that **prisons continue to receive weaker harm reduction coverage despite higher levels of drug-related risk and vulnerability than the general community.**

Comparing availability of key HR services in Prison vs in the Community (n=38 cities)

Figure 5: Comparison of available key harm reduction services in the community vs in prison settings

Apply equivalence of care to harm reduction: Where a harm reduction service already exists in the community, prison systems must be required to explain its absence inside prison.

→ Harm reduction services often still stop at prison gates. Prison settings should not have weaker harm reduction coverage. The Nelson Mandela Rules are clear: people in prison should enjoy the same standard of healthcare available in the community, and prison health services should be organised in close relationship with public health services [4][15].

initiate drug use after incarceration, restricted access to OAT initiation may create a barrier for people who develop opioid-related needs during imprisonment.

→ Medication options also remains limited, with methadone being the most commonly reported OAT medication available.

→ Naloxone on release was reported in only 7 out of 38 cities. This leaves a major gap at one of the highest-risk moments, when people leave prison and overdose risk is known to rise.

Spotlight: Are women's prisons being left behind?

Women's prisons may be at risk of being underserved in harm reduction services compared to men's prisons in the same city. Even though women remain a minority of the prison population, the number of incarcerated women has risen 57% in the last two decades (compared with 20% for men's) [16]. International evidence shows that harm reduction services in prison are more often absent for women and gender-diverse people who do drugs despite having greater primary healthcare and mental health needs, as well as higher prevalence of blood-borne infections and HIV. It is therefore **necessary that women's prisons have the same access to harm reducing services as men's**. Prisons must comply with the Bangkok rules for gender sensitive prison management and healthcare [17][18].

Who can receive harm reduction in prison?

— Available ≠ accessible to all

C-EHRN monitoring data shows that:

→ Access to harm reduction services can vary within the same city: services reported as available may not be equally available across all prisons.

→ OAT could only be started in prison in 25 cities. Considering that around one third of people who use drugs in prison reported to

Frontline Voice - FP Athens

"OAT exists in prison but with very limited access and medication options. Also, OAT is not available in the women's prison."

Prisons cannot remain in the shadows. Keep prison health and harm reduction visible, current, and accountable:

→ Need for consistent prison monitoring to stop responding to outdated problems, overlooking emerging harms, and pushing for services that do not match current needs.

Barriers to Data Collection

Some C-EHRN focal points reported difficulties in obtaining prison data, pointing to a **wider transparency problem**. Limited transparency makes it difficult to track what is actually happening inside prisons: not only which services exist, but how they work in practice, what harms remain uncovered, and what new challenges are emerging.

Council of Europe prison health guidance notes that in many countries there is still no precise answer to basic prison health questions because of a lack of systematically collected data [13].

The EUDA calls for a monitoring framework to improve information availability and harmonisation in order to support further development of monitoring drug-related activities in prisons across Europe [19].

Additionally, European prison monitoring standards require regular visits to places of detention that should lead to reports and concrete recommendations to improve the protection of prison populations [20].

Frontline Voice - FP Lisbon

"Prisons are a different world, closed from the outside and it's difficult to have information about what is going on inside, unless for those who are working close to them."

Want to know more about Harm Reduction services in prison?

→ The complete overview of the collected prison data and figures can be found in C-EHRNs [monitoring dashboard](#). This report is part of the C-EHRN 2025 monitoring. For other related publications see C-EHRN [Monitoring_page](#).

[Monitoring Dashboard](#)

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